

Changes in Renal Function and Oxidative Stress Status Associated with the Biochemical Effects of Calcium Carbide Ripened Plantain in Wistar Rats

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Abstract

The unnatural post-harvest ripening of fruits with toxic agents like calcium carbide has assumed public health concern. This study evaluated the effects of diets formulated with naturally ripened plantain (NRP) and calcium carbide-ripened plantain (CRP) on kidney function parameters, oxidative stress biomarkers, and histopathology in albino Wistar rats. Eighteen male rats weighing 120 ± 4.25 g were randomly assigned to three (3) groups ($n = 6$). Groups I (control), II and III were fed normal rat chow, diet formulated with NRP, and CRP, respectively. Biochemical analyses were performed on the blood samples of experimental rats, while the oxidative stress levels and histology of the kidneys were also assessed after the 35-day period of experiment. There were significant increases ($p < 0.05$) in serum creatinine, potassium, and chloride levels in CRP group when compared with the control and NRP groups, while serum sodium levels were significantly elevated in both NRP and CRP groups. Serum urea levels showed a non-significant ($p > 0.05$) reduction in CRP group when compared with both the control and NRP groups. Oxidative stress markers (superoxide dismutase-SOD, catalase-CAT and glutathione peroxidase-GPx) activities, protein concentration, and malondialdehyde levels did not differ significantly ($p > 0.05$) among the groups. Histopathology revealed normal kidney structure in the control and NRP groups. However, there were alterations in the kidney architecture of rats in the CRP group. Our findings suggest potential health risks associated with consuming calcium carbide-ripened fruits and emphasize the need for better and safer ripening practices.

Keywords: Calcium carbide, Oxidative stress, Plantain, Post-harvest ripening, Renal health

1.0 Introduction

Dietary foods play a vital role in ensuring food security and meeting the daily nutritional needs of populations in many regions, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa [1], where its absence has led to starvation, malnutrition, conflicts and deaths. These foods are valued for their capacity to supply essential nutrients required for growth, physiological maintenance, and metabolic regulation [2]. However, the growing demand for dietary crops owing to increased population, war, famine, climate change, etc., has put pressure on production, processing, and distribution practices, raising concerns about post-harvest handling, food quality, and consumer safety [3].

Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) is one of the most widely consumed dietary crops in tropical regions,

especially across West Africa, where it contributes significantly to dietary energy intake [4]. Its popularity is largely attributed to its high caloric value, affordability, and rich nutritional composition, including carbohydrates, dietary fibre, essential vitamins, minerals, and bioactive phytochemicals that support normal physiological and metabolic functions [2, 5, 6]. Africa ditto Nigeria is currently recognized as one of the leading plantain-producing regions globally, reflecting its importance in regional food systems and economies [7, 8]. Despite its nutritional and economic significance, plantain is a seasonal fruit with a high perishability rate, making it susceptible to post-harvest losses during transportation, storage, and marketing [9, 10]. To bridge this gap and meet increasing consumer demand, artificial ripening practices have become common, particularly in informal markets within

developing economies like Nigeria [11, 12]. These practices are primarily adopted to accelerate ripening, enhance visual appeal, and ensure continuous market supply for profit [13].

Several chemical agents are employed to induce artificial ripening, including ethylene, acetylene, ethylene glycol, and calcium carbide [14 – 16]. Among these, calcium carbide is frequently used because of its low cost, ease of application, and availability. Upon contact with moisture, calcium carbide releases acetylene gas, which mimics the action of ethylene, the natural plant hormone responsible for fruit ripening [17]. However, calcium carbide is not approved for use in food and often contains toxic impurities such as arsenic and phosphorous compounds, posing potential health risks to unsuspecting consumers [18, 19]. Therefore, this study seeks to increase the level of awareness of this unwholesome practice of chemically induced artificial ripening by evaluating the effects of calcium carbide-ripened plantain on some kidney function parameters and renal oxidative stress status in male albino Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus*).

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Fruit collection and ripening

Matured unripe plantain bunches were collected from a local farm in Ovia North-East Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria, in October of 2023. They were sorted, and divided into two groups. One group was allowed to ripen naturally in polythene bags stored in an isolated cupboard at room temperature, while the other group was artificially ripened using 10 g of calcium carbide in polyethylene bags under similar conditions, following common local practices. Ripening was monitored daily on peel colour changes using an industrial ripening scale (stages 1 – 7) as described by [20, 21].

2.2 Plant preparation

The naturally and calcium carbide-ripened plantain fruits were peeled, and the pulps were cut into small pieces and air-dried. Drying was continued until constant weight was achieved, after which the samples were pulverized into fine powder with the aid of a mortar and pestle and incorporated into the formulated diets used for the study.

2.3 Feed formulation

Experimental diets were formulated using dried powered plantain (naturally and artificially ripened) alongside other nutrients sources, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Dietary composition of feeds

Nutritional Composition of Feed	Percentage (%)
Carbohydrate (Plantain)	65.0
Protein (Cray Fish)	20.0
Fats (Butter)	5.0
Fiber (Wood shaft)	4.0
Mineral Mixture	3.5
Vitamin Mixture	1.3
Amino Acids (Met, Lys, Trp, Arg)	1.0
Choline	0.2
Total	100%

2.4 Animal handling

Eighteen (18) male Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) weighing 120 – 150 g, bred in the Animal House, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Benin were used for this study. The animals were housed in galvanized cages and allowed to acclimatize for one week under a 12-h light/dark cycle. Animal handling and experimental procedures were conducted in accordance with the guidelines of [22].

2.5 Experimental design

The rats were randomly assigned into three groups (n = 6 per group). Animals were allowed free access to food and water throughout the experimental period of 35 days.

Group 1 (Control): rats were given distilled water and fed standard rat chow

Group 2 (NRP): rats were fed diet formulated with naturally-ripened plantain (NRP)

Group 3 (CRP): rats were fed diet formulated with carbide-ripened plantain (CRP)

At the end of the 35-day feeding period and after an overnight fast, the rats were euthanized through cervical dislocation and blood samples collected via cardiac puncture into plain tubes for biochemical assays. The kidneys were excised and a portion was homogenized for oxidative stress studies, while the remainder were sectioned for histology analysis.

2.6 Biochemical assays

Blood samples were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min to obtain serum, which was used to determine blood urea nitrogen-BUN (Urease-Berthelot method [23]), creatinine [24], sodium and potassium [25], and chloride [26] ions. The kidney tissues were homogenized in ice-cold PBS and centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 min. The resulting supernatants were refrigerated until needed for the determination of SOD [27], CAT [28] and GPx [29] activities, MDA [30] and protein [31] concentrations.

2.7 Histopathology

The kidney tissue samples were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin, processed using standard histological procedures [32], and embedded in paraffin wax. Sections of approximately 5 μ m thickness were prepared, mounted on glass slides, and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) dye. Stained sections were examined under a light microscope for histological alterations.

2.8 Data analysis

Data were expressed as mean \pm SD. The analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism version 10.0 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for the analyses, followed by Tukey's posthoc test for multiple comparisons. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3.0 Results

3.1 Effect of Formulated Diets on Serum Creatinine, Urea and Electrolytes in the Kidneys of Wistar Rats

The effects of diets formulated with CRP and NRP on serum creatinine, urea, and electrolytes levels are presented in Table 2. Animals fed CRP diet showed significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in serum levels of creatinine and a non-significant decrease ($p > 0.05$) in urea concentration when compared with the normal control and NRP groups. There were also, significant increases ($p < 0.05$) in the serum levels of sodium, potassium, and chloride ions in the CRP and NRP fed groups when compared with the control group.

Table 2: Kidney function parameters of rats fed with formulated diets

Group	Creatinine (mg/ μ L)	Urea (mg/ μ L)	Na ⁺ (mg/ μ L)	K ⁺ (mg/ μ L)	Cl ⁻ (mg/ μ L)
NC	0.65 \pm 0.08	17.59 \pm 3.21	34.00 \pm 3.31	46.22 \pm 8.21	55.80 \pm 6.10
NRP	0.71 \pm 0.08 ^{bc}	17.67 \pm 1.60 ^c	41.47 \pm 3.40 ^{*c}	56.88 \pm 3.40 ^{bc}	67.80 \pm 6.58 ^{*b}
CRP	0.86 \pm 0.07 ^{*a}	13.19 \pm 2.66 ^c	42.14 \pm 4.24 [*]	86.47 \pm 4.24 ^{*a}	77.90 \pm 9.55 ^{*a}

Values are presented as Mean \pm SD, n = 6. * = significantly different from control group. a = significantly different from NRP groups. b = significantly different from CRP group. c = non-significantly different from control group. NC: Normal Control, NRP: Naturally Ripened Plantain, CRP: Carbide Ripened Plantain.

3.2 Effect of Formulated Diets on Antioxidant Enzymes, Protein Concentration and Lipid Peroxidation in the Kidneys of Wistar Rats

The effects of CRP and NRP formulated diets on kidney SOD, CAT, and GPx activities, protein concentration, and lipid peroxidation are presented in Table 3. There was a non-significant

($p > 0.05$) increase in the activities of SOD, CAT and GPx, as well as protein concentration in CRP-fed rats when compared with rats of the control group. Meanwhile, malondialdehyde concentration non-significantly ($p > 0.05$) increased in CRP-fed group when compared with the control and NRP groups.

Table 3: Levels of oxidative stress biomarkers and protein in rats fed formulated diets

Group	SOD (μ /g prot.)	CAT (μ /g prot.)	GPx (μ /g prot.)	Protein (g/dL)	MDA (μ /g prot.)
NC	2.20 \pm 0.43	0.79 \pm 0.17	2.83 \pm 0.56	0.85 \pm 0.17	0.77 \pm 0.10
NRP	2.35 \pm 0.73 ^c	0.85 \pm 0.26 ^c	3.06 \pm 0.93 ^c	0.83 \pm 0.25 ^c	0.61 \pm 0.24 ^c
CRP	2.39 \pm 0.54 ^c	0.89 \pm 0.20 ^c	3.13 \pm 0.66 ^c	0.77 \pm 0.23 ^c	0.79 \pm 0.43 ^c

Values are presented as Mean \pm SD, n = 6. c = non-significantly different from control group. NC: Normal Control, NRP: Naturally Ripened Plantain, CRP: Carbide Ripened Plantain, SOD: Superoxide Dismutase, CAT: Catalase, GPx: Glutathione Peroxidase, MDA: Malondialdehyde.

3.3 Histology of Rats Kidneys Exposed to Naturally Ripened and Calcium Carbide-Ripened Plantain

The photomicrographs of kidney sections from rats fed NRP and CRP are presented in Plate 1.

Kidney sections from the control and NRP-fed groups showed normal renal structure, with well-preserved glomeruli and tubules. In contrast, sections from CRP-fed rats showed atrophy of the renal corpuscle within the glomerulus when compared with the control group.

Plate 1: Photomicrograph of kidney sections. (A) Control, rats administered water only, histology revealed prominent renal corpuscle with glomerulus (long arrow) and tubules (short arrow) (B) Rats fed NRP diet showed prominent renal corpuscle with glomerulus (long arrow) and tubules (short arrow) (C) Rats exposed to CRP diet revealed atrophied renal corpuscle in the glomerulus (long arrow) with tubules (short arrow) (H&E x40).

4.0 Discussion

Calcium carbide is widely used as a chemical ripening agent in many developing countries despite concerns regarding its safety [17]. Exposure to calcium carbide has been associated with biochemical and structural alterations in vital organs [33]. The present study evaluated the effects of diets formulated with naturally ripened plantain (NRP) and calcium carbide-ripened

plantain (CRP) on serum creatinine, urea, electrolytes, some oxidative stress parameters, and the histology of the kidneys of albino Wistar rats.

Serum creatinine is a metabolic by-product of creatine phosphate metabolism in muscle and is eliminated almost exclusively through glomerular filtration, making it a reliable indicator of kidney function [34]. In this study, rats fed CRP exhibited a significant elevation in serum

creatinine levels compared with the control and NRP groups, indicating compromised glomerular filtration ability. A similar finding was reported by [35], who linked increased creatinine levels to renal injury following exposure to chemically ripened fruits. Blood urea concentration is another commonly used biomarker for the assessment of kidney function [36]. It was observed that serum urea levels showed a non-significant reduction in the CRP groups, suggesting that urea excretion was not markedly impaired under the experimental conditions. This finding agrees with the report of [37], who observed reduced serum urea levels in Wistar rats exposed to calcium carbide-ripened fruits. The rationale for the reduction in urea reported in that study was attributed to alterations in protein metabolism or hepatic urea synthesis rather than overt renal failure. Similarly, the reduced urea levels observed in this study may reflect dietary influences, compensatory metabolic mechanisms, or adaptive renal handling of nitrogenous wastes [38]. For instance, there was a reduced protein concentration in animals fed CRP, suggesting an adaptive renal handling of nitrogenous wastes by exposed animals. Nonetheless, it may be inferred that urea levels may be a less sensitive marker of early kidney dysfunction as against creatinine concentration observed in this study.

Electrolytes such as sodium, potassium, and chloride play essential roles in fluid balance, neuromuscular function, and acid–base homeostasis, and their regulation is tightly controlled by the kidneys [39]. In this study, serum sodium levels were significantly increased in both NRP and CRP groups, which may be related to dietary mineral contribution or altered renal sodium handling. In contrast, potassium and chloride levels were markedly elevated only in the CRP group, suggesting impaired tubular reabsorption or altered membrane permeability resulting from renal injury. Variations in electrolyte levels may be influenced by factors including, duration of exposure, quantity of toxicant (e.g., calcium carbide) used, dietary composition, and experimental design. Nonetheless, [40] remarked that disturbances in potassium and chloride balance are clinically significant and may predispose to acid–base imbalance and cardiovascular complications.

Oxidative stress is a recognized mechanism through which chemical toxicants exert organ damage, particularly in metabolically active organs such as the kidney [41, 42]. It arises from

an imbalance between reactive oxygen species generation and antioxidant defenses function [43]. From this study, there were slight increases in antioxidant enzyme (SOD, CAT, and GPx) activities followed by a non-significant increase in lipid peroxidation in rats fed CRP diet compared to the control rats. These mild variations align with the early phase of oxidative stress. Our findings corroborate that of [44], who reported altered antioxidant enzyme activities and increased lipid peroxidation following ingestion of calcium carbide-ripened fruits. The absence of significant oxidative alterations in this study may be attributed to the duration of exposure, dietary formulation, or other compensatory metabolic factors like enhanced inbuilt antioxidant defense system of the experimental animals [45].

Histopathological findings correlate evidence of kidney tissue alteration with earlier biochemical results. While the kidney tissues from rats fed NPR exhibited normal architecture comparable to the control group, rats fed CRP showed atrophy of the renal corpuscle within the glomerulus. This structural distortion is indicative of glomerular injury and corroborates the observed elevation of serum creatinine earlier mentioned. Similar histological alterations, including glomerular degeneration and tubular damage, have been reported following exposure to chemical toxicants [46]. Such changes are of toxicological importance, as they may represent early structural damage that could progress to chronic renal dysfunction with prolonged exposure [47].

5.0 Conclusion

This study shows that CRP altered kidney biochemical parameters and histology, indicating potential nephrotoxicity. Rats fed these forced-ripened plantains exhibited elevated serum creatinine, electrolytes perturbations, and glomerular changes. The findings highlight health risks associated with chemically ripened fruits, especially with calcium-carbide, and underscore the need for stricter regulations and public health enlightenment.

6.0 Recommendation

1. An extended study is recommended to evaluate the long-term biochemical effect of calcium carbide ripened plantain on multiple organs.

7.0 Funding

This research received no external funding.

8.0 Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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